

IOT Based Speaker Automation System Using FPGA

Dr Manoj Kumar

Department of ECE, NIT Manipur, Langol, Imphal . Manipur, India

Abstract— The Internet of Things (IoT) is very useful in automation due to the availability of the internet everywhere. In this work, an IoT-based speaker automation system is developed for real-time use in emergency situations such as fire alarms, flood alarms, etc. The proposed system consists of a NODE MCU ESP8266 board, a Basys3 Artix7 FPGA (Field Programmable Gate Array) board, and a Black Round Frame Mini Speaker. The Blynk console and Blynk IoT app are used to remotely control the speaker. Two switches of the Blynk console or Blynk IoT app are used to control two types of music on the speaker. Two types of music and interfacing of FPGA with ESP8266 are done by the Xilinx Vivado 2015.2 tool. The Verilog language is used to design two types of music, and the VHDL language is used for designing interfacing with the ESP8266 board. The proposed system consumes 74 FFs, 118 LUTs, and 0.075 W of power. The proposed system can be easily used for setting reminders and alarms for emergency situations.

Keywords—FPGA, IOT, ESP8266, Blynk, VHDL

I. INTRODUCTION

Smart speakers are used in many areas, such as voice commands, calls and communications, smart home control, music playback and streaming, entertainment and media control and personal organization. Smart speakers can also be used in language translation, solving math problems, telling jokes and weather briefings. Most of the smart speakers are used for building smart homes to make our daily lives easy. IoT-based speaker automation refers to automatically controlling speakers from anywhere in the world by using the internet. By using IoT, data can be transferred from one place to another place without any interaction between human to human or human to computer [1]. By combining IoT with FPGA, a developed system is more reliable, flexible, and less costly, and can be used for the long term [2,3]. IoT-based speaker automation systems can be very useful in flood control, fire control, hospital control and industrial control. In this work, an IoT-based speaker automation system is developed for real-time applications. The proposed system uses ESP8266 as Wi-Fi technology to build wireless communication between speakers and users. A speaker with two music is remotely accessible via blynk cloud or blynk app for any emergency situations. In this work, Verilog, VHDL language and Arduino programming are used for designing the proposed system and ESP8266, an FPGA board, is used for implementing the proposed architecture. The proposed system consumes less area and power and operates at higher speed.

Many researchers have been working on integrating IoT with FPGA for building real-time systems. Paper [4]

develops an IoT-based home automation system to automatically control fans, tube lights, gas leakages and air conditioners. The proposed system is equipped with various sensors and ESP8266 is used as a microcontroller for gathering the sensor data. Authors in paper [5] use Elbert V2 Spartan 3A FPGA as a specific processor to develop a home automation system. This system uses short message service (SMS) to control devices in five different rooms. An advanced home automation based on FPGA and an Android mobile device was developed by the authors in the paper [6]. The Android device uses speech recognition to control light and DC motor. An economical home monitoring system based on IoT was developed in Paper [7]. The proposed system was developed using an Arduino uno board, sensor, GSM module, camera, and user interface module. This system monitors doors by using a camera. In paper [8], an IoT-based hardware implementation of various image processing filters is discussed. The proposed system was designed using Verilog and implemented on a ZedBoard Zynq 7000 APSoC board. A Gaussian filter, average filter, and sharpen filter were used for performing filtering operations on LENA's image, and a VGA monitor was used to display the input and output images. An Altera Cyclone IV EP4CE22F17C6N FPGA and ESP8266-based embedded architecture was developed by the authors in Paper[9] to control the air conditioning unit and lighting. A web interface coded in JavaScript was developed to configure and monitor the proposed IoT-based home automation system. FPGA and GSM-based for real-time monitoring and controlling various home appliances were developed by authors in paper [10]. Authors in paper [11] use a smartphone app to pass commands to the FPGA to control home appliances. An IoT-based home automation was developed by the authors in paper [12] using an FPGA, an ESP8266 board and an Android mobile phone.

II. PROPOSED IOT BASED SPEAKER AUTOMATION SYSTEM

A block diagram for the proposed IOT-based speaker automation system is shown in Figure 1. The proposed system contains an Artix7 Basys3 FPGA board, an ESP8266 board as a Wi-Fi module, and a black round frame mini speaker. Blynk cloud or Blynk IOT app is used to remotely control the speaker. The interfacing of the ESP8266, the FPGA, and speaker is shown in Table I.

Figure.1: Block diagram for the proposed IOT based speaker automation system

Table I: Pinout diagram for the proposed IOT based speaker automation system

FPGA Symbol	ESP8266 Symbol	Details	Pin	Input/Output
clk		System Clock	W5	input
speaker		Speaker input	A16	output
en		Music0	B15	input
en1		Music1	B16	input
	ledpin	Switch0 for Blynk	D0	output
	ledpin1	Switch1 for Blynk	D2	output

To generate two types of music, various note values are stored in two ROMs. Verilog language is used to design the two music architectures and VHDL language is used to design the main module for interfacing FPGA with the ESP8266 and Speaker. When ledpin is high than music0 is active to act as an alarm, and when ledpin1 is high, then music1 is active to act as an alarm. Both these ESP8266 pins are used to remotely control the speaker via Blynk cloud or Blynk IOT app. Figure2 represents the diagram for designing the proposed system by mixing VHDL and the Verilog language. Figure3 represents the design of the IOT module using ESP8266.

Figure.2: Design of top module using VHDL

Figure.3: Design of IOT module using ESP8266

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS FOR THE PROPOSED SPEAKER CONTROL SYSTEM

Generated music from the proposed system are freely available on the following websites: Music0:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1r-TxQ1_o6wNfK70uq0j8iOopDn3H2H1j/view?usp=drive_link

Music1:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1yc1DSGOTOHCQb3COKNKVX9xjCXF6Fxiz/view?usp=drive_link

The proposed system is implemented on a Basys3 Artix7 FPGA board with target device xc7a35tcbg236-1. An experimental set-up diagram for the implemented IOT-based speaker automation system is shown in Figure.4. Blynk cloud allows developers to connect microcontrollers, sensors, and other devices to remotely control them via android mobile or web applications. A diagram for the Blynk cloud for remotely controlling speakers is shown in Figure.5. Blynk IOT diagram for remotely controlling proposed system is shown in Figure.6 Figure.7 represents an RTL diagram for the proposed IOT-based speaker automation system. Synthesis results for the IOT-based speaker automation system are shown in Table II.

Figure.4: Experimental set up diagram for the proposed IOT based speaker automation system

Figure.5: Diagram of the Blynk Cloud interface

Figure .6: Blynk IOT diagram

Figure.7: RTL diagram for the IOT based speaker automation system

Table II: Synthesis results for the IOT based speaker automation system

Total on chip power consumption(W)	Speed(ns)	Resources	Utilization
0.075	3.464	FF	74
		LUT	118
		BRAM	0.5

Proposed system consumes 74 FF, 118 LUTs and 0.5 BRAM. It operates at 289MHz and consumes 0.075W of power.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this work, an IoT-based speaker automation system is developed using a Basys3 Artix7 FPGA board, ESP8266 Board and Black Round Frame Mini Speaker. The proposed prototype can be easily assembled for use as a real-time alarm system for handling any emergency situation. Blynk cloud or Blynk IoT app is used for accessing the two types of music. This music can use an alarm audio tone for handling any emergency situation. As the proposed prototype is developed using FPGA board, it can be reconfigured and be more reliable. Two LED switches of Blynk cloud are used to trigger two types of music. This system is designed using

VHDL, Verilog and Arduino uno programming languages, and it can be easily controlled remotely. All experimental outputs are shown in this work. The proposed prototype consumes less area, less power and operates at higher speed. In future work, other types of music can be added to this prototype to make it more beneficial for real-time use.

Funding

Not applicable

REFERENCES

1. Santosh Wagaj and Pooja More, "IOT based home automation system using FPGA", International Journal of Advances in Engineering and Management (IJAEM) Volume 3, Issue 7, pp: 2180-2182, July 2021.
2. Amirah Aisha Badrul Hisham, Mohamad HafisIzranIshaka, Chan , Zaharuddin Mohameda, KokTeika and Nurul HawaniIdrisb, "Bluetooth-Based Home Automation System Using an Android Phone," Jurnal Teknologi (Sciences & Engineering), Vol.70, No. 3, pp.57–61, 2014.
3. Bader M. O. Al-thobaiti, Iman I. M.Abosolaiman, Mahdi H. M. Alzahrani, Sami H. A. Almalki, and Mohamed S. Soliman, "Design and Implementation of a Reliable Wireless RealTime Home Automation System Based on Arduino Uno Single-Board Microcontroller," International Journal of Control, Automation and Systems, Vol.3, No.3, pp .11-15, July 2014.
4. Voore Subba Rao, Mahesh Kumar Thota, N. Santhosh Ramchander and K. Ramya Laxmi, "Internet of Things (IoT) based Home Automation System (HAS) Implementation of Real-Time Experiment", International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology (IJERT), Volume 9, Issue 11, pp.200-204,2021.
5. C Chandra Murali, Dr S Aruna Mastani, and K Srinivasa Rao, "HOME AUTOMATION CHIP ON FPGA", Journal Of Technology, Vol 13 Issue 10,2021.
6. Sweatha K N, Poornima M, and Vinutha M H, "Advance Home Automation Using FPGA Controller", International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer and Communication Engineering Vol. 2, Issue 7, July 2013.
7. Obheroi, K.S.,Chaurasia, A.,Choudhury, T., Kumar,P, "Economical Home Monitoring System Using IOT", Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference on Computational Intelligence and Informatics, Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing", Vol.712. Springer, Singapore,2018.
8. Rupani,A,Whig,P.,Sujediya ,G.,Vyas,P, " Hardware Implementation of IoT Based Image Processing Filters", Proceedings of the 2nd International

- Conference on Computational Intelligence and Informatics, Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing”, Vol.712. Springer, Singapore,2018.
9. Chee-Pun. Ooi, Wooi-Haw. Tan, Soon-Nyeon. Cheong, Yee-Lien. Lee, V. M. Baskaran, Yeong-Liang. Low,” FPGA-based embedded architecture for IoT home automation application”, Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science, Vol. 14, No. 2, pp. 646~652, May 2019.
 10. Madhuri R Mukkawar and S. D. Sawant,” Home Automation through FPGA Controller”, International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology (IJERT), Vol. 3 Issue 3, March – 2014.
 11. Tanvi Gurav, Ibrahim Gaonkhadkar, Soham Deolekar, Yash Dhanawade, and Rashmi Kulkarni, ”IOT based Home Automation using FPGA”, International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts (IJCRT) ,Volume 10 ,Issue4, April 2022.
 12. Aadesh Pawar, Shubham Gurav, Vanshika Parkar, Swarnima Patole and Satendra Mane,” IoT based home automation using FPGA”, International Journal of Advanced Research, Ideas and Innovations in Technology, Volume 7, Issue 5,2021.